

Recent and Upcoming Activities

We are organising a number of events for the upcoming months. See the full list on:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/>

or follow us on Twitter:

<https://twitter.com/esiwace/>

Access our results

All our results – publications and reports – are available on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/>

Peer-reviewed publications are accessible via OpenAIRE:

<https://explore.openaire.eu/>

We support Open Access!

Initial cloud distribution for demonstrator using a very high resolution global atmosphere model.

At a glance

esiwace
CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER
AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

Title: Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe

Instrument: European research infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures) · work programme 2014-2015 · Call: EINFRA-5-2015 · Topic H2020-EINFRA-2015-1 (RIA), H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. · Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures

EC Contribution: 4.95 million €

Duration: 1 Sep 2015 – 31 Aug 2019

Consortium: 16 partners from seven countries

Project Coordinator: Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ), Germany

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Project Objectives

ESiWACE substantially improves efficiency and productivity of numerical **weather** and **climate** simulation on **high-performance computing (HPC)** platforms by supporting the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modeling (ESM).

A special focus is the establishment of high-resolution global simulation demonstrators which will, once pushed towards production on exascale systems in future, open up entirely new research opportunities and perspectives.

Project Impacts

Weather and **climate** computing has always been among the key drivers for **HPC** development, with domain-specific scientific and technical requirements that stretch the capability and capacity of existing soft- and hardware to the limits.

Performing co-design at hard- and software level, ESiWACE directly interacts with and impacts on the industrial **HPC** eco-system and fosters collaboration of **weather** and **climate** science, **HPC** research and industry at the European scale.

High-Resolution Demonstrators

A key target is to reach global models with spatial resolutions that allow simulating convective clouds and small-scale ocean eddies. This will provide much more fidelity in the representation of high-impact regional events. Global cloud resolving models need spatial resolutions of at least 1 km. ESIWACE aims at enabling the implementation and operation of the infrastructures required to address the **HPC** challenges presented by this class of science cases.

Scalability of IFS- and ICON-based atmosphere-only global high-resolution demonstrators.

ESiWACE Themes

The **scalability** theme coordinates performance assessment and upgrade development of high-resolution **weather** and **climate** models, tools, coupling and I/O technologies to provide the simulation technology required at exascale.

The **usability** theme focuses on the ease-of-use of available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures for Earth system models on current peta-scale supercomputers.

The **exploitability** theme addresses major data handling barriers that pose severe bottlenecks in **HPC** for data-intensive ESM.

Governance and Engagement

ESiWACE follows a user-driven approach. A major aim is therefore to create and sustain a governance structure which ensures that the users from the **weather** and **climate** community inside and outside the ESIWACE consortium are actively involved in both

- the development of the high-resolution demonstrators, and
- the definition of scope and priorities of the ESIWACE agenda and related services.

ESiWACE therefore leverages two established European networks: the European Network for Earth system modeling (ENES) and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

ENES: <https://portal.enes.org/>

ECMWF: <http://www.ecmwf.int/>

The Consortium

ESiWACE is coordinated by DRKZ and brings together 16 partners from seven countries having outstanding expertise in the fields of weather, climate and HPC.

Coordinator:

WEATHER

CLIMATE

HPC

